

Spontaneous Heterotopic Pregnancy in a Patient With HIV Infection: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Heterotopic pregnancy, defined as the coexistence of an intrauterine and an extrauterine gestation, is a rare and potentially life-threatening condition. Its incidence in spontaneous conceptions is estimated at 1 in 30,000, but it may increase up to 300-fold with the use of assisted reproductive technologies. In women with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection, the higher prevalence of sexually transmitted infections and pelvic inflammatory disease may further increase the risk of this entity. **Case report:** A 33-year-old woman with controlled HIV infection on antiretroviral therapy presented to the emergency department with sudden-onset abdominal pain and scant vaginal bleeding. Ultrasound revealed a 9-week intrauterine pregnancy and a ruptured left tubal ectopic pregnancy with hemoperitoneum. Exploratory laparotomy with left salpingectomy was performed, preserving the intrauterine gestation. The pregnancy progressed without complications and concluded with an elective cesarean section at 38 weeks, yielding a healthy newborn. **Discussion:** Diagnosing heterotopic pregnancy in patients with HIV is challenging, as the identification of an intrauterine pregnancy may erroneously lead to ruling out a concurrent ectopic gestation. Transvaginal ultrasound with systematic adnexal evaluation is essential for early diagnosis. In cases of rupture and hemoperitoneum, immediate surgical intervention is the standard management, with the possibility of preserving the intrauterine pregnancy. **Conclusion:** This case—only the second reported in the literature involving an HIV-positive patient and the first to achieve a term intrauterine pregnancy following ectopic surgery—highlights the need to maintain a high index of suspicion even in spontaneous conceptions. It also underscores the importance of a multidisciplinary approach, timely diagnosis, and prompt surgical treatment to optimize maternal and fetal outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Heterotopic pregnancy, HIV, ectopic pregnancy, salpingectomy, intrauterine pregnancy.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
06 December 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

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INTRODUCTION

Heterotopic pregnancy is defined as the presence of two or more simultaneous gestations in different locations, typically one intrauterine and one ectopic.¹ It is considered a rare and potentially life-threatening condition, with an approximate incidence of 1 in 30,000 spontaneous conceptions; however, its incidence may increase up to 300-fold (approximately 1 in every 100 pregnancies), with reported rates ranging from 0.15% to 1% following the use of assisted reproductive technologies.^{2,3}

Risk factors associated with ectopic and heterotopic pregnancy include advanced maternal age, smoking, endometriosis, and the use of an intrauterine device, among others. Nevertheless, the most frequent risk factors linked to heterotopic pregnancy are a history of ectopic pregnancy, previous pelvic inflammatory disease (genital tract infections such as *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Chlamydia trachomatis*, and *Trichomonas vaginalis* are more common in women with HIV), abdominal adhesions, tubal surgery, and, in some reports, antiretroviral therapy for human immunodeficiency virus (HIV).⁴⁻⁸

Most heterotopic pregnancies occur in the fallopian tubes and are diagnosed primarily (70%) between 5 and 8 weeks of gestation.^{11,12} Diagnosis becomes less frequent as gestational age increases, with approximately 20% identified between 9 and 11 weeks, and fewer than 10% after 11 weeks.^{4,12}

Given the diagnostic challenges of heterotopic pregnancy, symptoms such as abdominal pain, enlarged uterus, peritoneal irritation, and adnexal masses have been identified as warning signs that should raise suspicion.¹² Early diagnosis may be difficult because symptoms are often absent.¹³

The most common differential diagnoses in the context of severe abdominal pain early in pregnancy include spontaneous abortion, ectopic pregnancy, intrauterine pregnancy with hemorrhagic corpus luteum, ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome after in vitro fertilization, and adnexal torsion. Nongynecologic causes—such as appendicitis, cholecystitis, bowel obstruction, and pancreatitis—must also be ruled out.^{14,15}

The cornerstone of proper diagnosis is a high index of suspicion combined with appropriate use of transvaginal ultrasound with systematic adnexal evaluation in the early first trimester; identification of an intrauterine pregnancy often leads to the erroneous exclusion of a simultaneous ectopic pregnancy.^{5,16}

Transvaginal ultrasound diagnosis of an ectopic gestation has a sensitivity of 71%–100% and a specificity of 41%–99%.¹³ However, definitive diagnosis is made by laparoscopy or laparotomy in 74% of cases.^{14,15}

Early diagnosis and prompt intervention can reduce possible complications such as tubal rupture, hypovolemic shock requiring blood transfusions, and compromise of both the intrauterine pregnancy and maternal outcome.^{13,17}

We report the case of a patient with a history of HIV who presented with a spontaneous heterotopic pregnancy,

consisting of a ruptured left tubal ectopic gestation and a concurrent intrauterine pregnancy that reached term.

CASE REPORT

A 33-year-old female patient, originally from the state of Chiapas and residing in Yucatán, of mestizo ethnicity, living in a common-law union, homemaker, with a history of habitual alcohol and tobacco use, presented to the emergency department. She had no relevant family medical history. She had been diagnosed with HIV infection four years earlier and had since been on combined antiretroviral therapy with emtricitabine/tenofovir (Truvada®), with full adherence and documented virological suppression.

Her gynecologic and obstetric history included menarche at age 14 and sexual debut at 17, with three known sexual partners and no contraceptive use. This was her fourth pregnancy; she had previously had a vaginal delivery at age 16, an incomplete abortion eight years earlier requiring surgical uterine evacuation, and a cesarean section two years prior, indicated to prevent vertical transmission of HIV. She did not recall her last menstrual period and had not received prenatal care. A cervical cytology performed six months earlier showed no abnormalities. She denied recent pelvic inflammatory disease, intrauterine device use, genital infections, or assisted reproductive interventions.

She arrived at the emergency department accompanied by paramedics, reporting a four-day history of scant vaginal bleeding and sudden-onset abdominal pain in the past four hours, localized to the hypogastrium and radiating to the left iliac fossa. The pain had progressively intensified, reaching 10/10 on the visual analog scale, and was associated with nausea and a single episode of non-bilious vomiting.

On arrival, vital signs showed hypotension (85/60 mmHg), heart rate of 86 bpm, respiratory rate of 20 breaths per minute, temperature of 36.4°C, and oxygen saturation of 98% on room air. The patient was alert and oriented, with an expression of pain and generalized pallor. Abdominal examination revealed decreased bowel sounds, guarding, and marked tenderness in the hypogastrium and left iliac fossa. On gynecological examination with speculscopy, the cervix was closed with evidence of non-active bleeding. Bimanual examination revealed a bulging posterior cul-de-sac, cervical motion tenderness, and an enlarged uterus measuring approximately 10 × 5 cm.

Given the clinical presentation suggestive of an acute gynecologic abdomen, an abdominopelvic ultrasound was performed. It showed a uterus measuring 113 × 40 × 53 mm with homogeneous myometrium and an intrauterine gestational sac with a viable embryo and cardiac activity, consistent with a 9-week pregnancy. Additionally, a second gestational sac was identified in the left adnexa, also containing an embryo with cardiac activity, as well as abundant free fluid in the abdominal cavity, compatible with hemoperitoneum.

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Initial laboratory studies reported hemoglobin of 9.6 g/dL, hematocrit of 28.6%, leukocytosis of $13.2 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$ (94% neutrophils), normal platelet count ($275 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$), coagulation times within acceptable ranges (PT 15.8 s, aPTT 26 s), creatinine of 0.76 mg/dL, and normal liver transaminases.

Suspecting a heterotopic pregnancy with left tubal rupture, an urgent exploratory laparotomy was performed. Intraoperatively, approximately 600 cc of hemoperitoneum was found, as well as an enlarged gravid uterus and a ruptured ectopic pregnancy located in the ampullary region of the left fallopian tube. The right adnexa was unremarkable. A left salpingectomy with peritoneal lavage and drainage was performed. The patient recovered favorably in the immediate postoperative period, achieving hemodynamic stability within 48 hours, at which time ultrasound confirmed persistence and viability of the intrauterine pregnancy.

During prenatal follow-up at the hospital, the patient completed eight control visits without obstetric complications. Her viral load remained undetectable (<20 copies/mL), and her CD4 lymphocyte count remained elevated (946 cells/ mm^3). Complementary studies—including liver function tests, urinalysis, oral glucose tolerance test, and viral screening for hepatitis B and C—were all within normal limits. Vaginal swab testing revealed

clue cells compatible with *Gardnerella vaginalis*, for which treatment with metronidazole suppositories was initiated every 24 hours for 10 days, with complete resolution of symptoms. Histopathological analysis of the surgical specimen showed a 4×1.5 cm segment of fallopian tube with vascular congestion and rupture, confirming the diagnosis of a ruptured tubal ectopic pregnancy.

At 38 weeks of gestation, with no signs of labor, an elective cesarean delivery was scheduled. A male newborn was delivered, weighing 2410 grams and measuring 48 cm in length, with APGAR scores of 8 and 9. Capurro assessment corresponded to 38 weeks of gestational age. A right fimbriectomy was performed as definitive contraception, and the prior surgical absence of the left tube was confirmed. No intraoperative or postoperative complications occurred.

The patient was discharged in satisfactory clinical condition 48 hours after the procedure, with pharmacologic lactation suppression and subsequent follow-up at the Center for HIV and Sexually Transmitted Infection Care (CAPASITS). No adverse events or complications were recorded. The diagnosis of heterotopic pregnancy was confirmed clinically, sonographically, and histologically, and timely surgical intervention allowed preservation of the intrauterine gestation, which progressed normally and resulted in a favorable neonatal outcome.

Figure 1. Left tubal ectopic pregnancy with visible gestational sac and embryo in the ampullary region.

DISCUSSION

The risk factors associated with heterotopic pregnancy largely overlap with those of ectopic pregnancy and include a history of prior ectopic pregnancy, tubal or uterine anatomical abnormalities, infertility treatments, pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), and previous tubal surgery.^{4,7,19} In patients with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), several of these factors may coexist. HIV, as a sexually transmitted infection, is associated with a higher prevalence of PID, which in turn constitutes a predisposing factor for

both ectopic and heterotopic pregnancies. Additionally, recent years have seen increased access of HIV-positive women—including those in serodiscordant partnerships—to assisted reproductive programs, adding a further risk factor for this condition.²⁰

Within this context, HIV infection may increase the risk of heterotopic pregnancy through two main mechanisms: first, tubal damage secondary to prior pelvic infections, and second, the more frequent use of assisted reproductive technologies among this population. Although clinical trials

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of antiretroviral therapy often exclude pregnant women or those seeking pregnancy, limiting data on conception rates and outcomes in this group, the World Health Organization's universal recommendation to initiate antiretroviral therapy in all individuals with HIV has increased the number of women who conceive while on treatment.⁹

In a multicenter study by Stringer et al. (2018) evaluating pregnancy outcomes among women with HIV, 64% of pregnancies resulted in live births (47% term, 53% preterm), 4% in stillbirths, 20% in spontaneous abortions, 11% in elective abortions, and 1% in ectopic pregnancies.⁹ These findings confirm that although uncommon, ectopic and heterotopic pregnancies are real complications in this population, requiring a high index of diagnostic suspicion.^{9,11} Savasi et al. reported a case of heterotopic pregnancy in a 30-year-old woman with controlled HIV infection (HAART, CD4 250/mm³), initially diagnosed with an intrauterine pregnancy and tubo-ovarian abscess. After antibiotic treatment and a legal abortion, she re-presented with hemoperitoneum; laparoscopy revealed a ruptured tubal ectopic pregnancy, and salpingectomy was performed. This report highlights that in women with HIV, the high prevalence of PID and tubo-ovarian abscesses—particularly in those with low CD4 counts—not only increases the risk of ectopic/heterotopic pregnancy but may also delay diagnosis by mimicking other gynecologic or infectious conditions.²¹ Management of heterotopic pregnancy is particularly complex due to the dual objective of preserving the intrauterine pregnancy while simultaneously removing the extrauterine pregnancy and mitigating its associated risks. Therapeutic decisions must be individualized based on hemodynamic stability, gestational age, and anatomic considerations. Surgery is indicated in the presence of hemoperitoneum or hemodynamic instability and remains the standard of care in ruptured tubal pregnancies, as it provides rapid and definitive resolution.^{4,18} When surgical intervention is required, approximately two-thirds of intrauterine pregnancies progress to live births, whereas one-third result in miscarriage, underscoring the need for careful, multidisciplinary management to optimize maternal and fetal outcomes.^{12,13,16}

In the present case, early surgical intervention, optimal virological control, and the absence of visible contralateral tubal damage were key factors in preserving and successfully completing the intrauterine pregnancy, leading to a favorable neonatal outcome without significant maternal complications.

Strengths in the management included timely ultrasonographic diagnosis, immediate surgical intervention in the presence of hemoperitoneum, continuation of antiretroviral therapy with viral suppression and high CD4 counts, and close prenatal monitoring with a multidisciplinary approach. Limitations included the lack of a known last menstrual period and absence of early prenatal care, which complicated gestational dating, as well as the

unavailability of laparoscopic management—which, in higher-resource centers, may reduce surgical morbidity.

Medical literature supports that when the ectopic component is ruptured or hemoperitoneum is present, immediate surgical resolution is the standard of care, with live birth rates for the intrauterine gestation approaching 66%. Previous reports emphasize the role of PID in increasing the risk of heterotopic pregnancy among HIV-positive patients and the potential for diagnostic delay.^{9–12} Our case aligns with the best outcomes reported when early intervention, effective hemostasis, and uterine preservation are combined, even in patients with controlled infectious comorbidity.

The conclusion that HIV may increase the risk of heterotopic pregnancy is supported by: an increased likelihood of tubal damage from prior PID, more frequent use of assisted reproductive technologies, and underreporting due to the exclusion of pregnant women from clinical trials. In the case presented, the patient's history of prior uterine curettage and the possibility of subclinical PID, along with the ampullary rupture of the ectopic pregnancy, constitute plausible causes. No evidence of contralateral tubal pathology or use of assisted reproduction was noted, suggesting a unilateral event involving a previously vulnerable tube.

Several key lessons emerge from this case: maintaining a high index of suspicion for heterotopic pregnancy in patients with HIV—even when a viable intrauterine gestational sac is documented—is essential; stabilizing the patient and providing immediate surgical resolution of the ruptured ectopic component is critical to preserving the intrauterine pregnancy; multidisciplinary management involving obstetrics, infectious diseases, and anesthesia optimizes outcomes; continuation of antiretroviral therapy is essential throughout pregnancy; and patient education should be reinforced to help recognize warning signs and promote early access to prenatal care.

From the patient's perspective, rapid pain relief after surgery, clear understanding of her diagnosis and therapeutic decisions, and satisfaction with the obstetric outcome and follow-up through CAPASITS were meaningful aspects of her experience. She also reported that the information received during her care strengthened her confidence in recognizing warning signs in future pregnancies.

CONCLUSIONS

Heterotopic pregnancy is a rare and potentially life-threatening condition whose incidence may be higher in women with HIV infection due to the elevated prevalence of sexually transmitted infections and pelvic inflammatory disease in this population. This case underscores the importance of considering this diagnosis even in spontaneous conceptions and in the presence of a confirmed intrauterine pregnancy. A comprehensive approach—including timely ultrasound diagnosis, immediate surgical intervention, continuation of antiretroviral therapy, and close prenatal monitoring—was essential to achieving a favorable

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maternal–fetal outcome. This case highlights the need for a high index of suspicion, systematic adnexal evaluation, and individualized selection of surgical approach to optimize prognosis, as well as the importance of reinforcing specialized obstetric surveillance in HIV-positive women.

Acknowledgments: Special thanks to the Agustín O’Horán General Hospital and the Faculty of Medicine of the Autonomous University of Yucatan.

Funding: None.

Conflict of interest: None.

Ethical considerations: The patient was informed at all times about the diagnosis, the procedures performed, and the potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for surgical and anesthetic interventions and for publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional guidelines of the hospital.

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